

Nanoplasmonic Cytokine Biosensor towards Precision Medicine

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Abstract—The framework of precision medicine envisions a world in which diseases are diagnosed not simply on the basis of a patient’s symptoms but on accumulated data that reveals the fundamental mechanistic bases of human diseases. This raises an emerging clinical demand for transformative tools/biosensors that can measure the biochemical and biological markers to understand the dynamical response of the patient status in a rapid and accurate manner. Nanoplasmonic biosensors have shown great promise to enable such phenotypic measurements with high precision, sensitivity, specificity and simplicity. In this paper, we present a gold nanorod based opto-microfluidic sensing platform for monitoring functional immune response and their translation in clinical applications towards precision medicine. Specifically, we show a label-free, barcode LSPR nanoplasmonic biosensor for high-throughput, multiplex detection of cytokine biomarkers in a complex serum matrix and patient serum samples. Our strategy of monitoring immune functions using optofluidic nanobiosensors achieved high accuracy and sensitivity with much less sample volume and shorter assay time than that of the conventional methods, which provides new insight into disease severity and therapeutic response and offers great potential in future medical treatment for personalized medicine.

Keywords- *localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR); nanoplasmonic sensing; cytokine; precision medicine*

I. INTRODUCTION

Cytokines, a group of bioactive immunomodulating proteins secreted by immune cells, play vital roles in regulation of cellular proliferation, differentiation, activation, intercellular communications, and inflammatory responses in immune system [1, 2]. Their multiplex roles in physiological functions render cytokines to be the key indicators of human immune status. Precise monitoring and quantifying cytokine release can thus provide valuable information of the rapidly changing immune conditions of the host during the course of a disease. Conventional methods for cytokine biomarker detection in clinical diagnosis are based on sandwich immunoassays. These techniques exhibit certain advantages of sensitive and robustness, but the time-consuming labeling and washing processes and an onset of undesirable photochemical reaction or photobleaching upon excitation prohibit real-time

and dynamic detection of cytokines in the host. The limitations in conventional sandwich-based immunoassays raise an emerging need for rapid, multiplex and high throughput cytokine assays from frequently sampled human blood.

Over the last two decades, plasmonic biosensing has been extensively studied owing to the proven advantages especially in real-time monitoring with minimal interference and high stability [3, 4]. Comparing to the conventional surface plasmon resonance (SPR) sensor limited by the bulky system and low spectral resolution [5, 6], LSPR-based biosensors have been perceived as emerging label-free optical biosensing techniques enabled by recent advances in nanotechnology. LSPR is a plasmonic phenomenon that arises around nanoscale structures or nanoparticles of noble metals when the incident light frequency matches the natural frequency of electron oscillation of the conductive metal nanoparticles. The resonance wavelength and intensity can be readily modified by the temporal or irreversible absorption of analytes, which permits high-sensitivity and real-time analysis of antibody-antigen binding. Since the sensor elements used in LSPR techniques could be as small as a few tens of nanometers, they are highly desirable for nano-scale biomolecule detection and possess great potentials in sensor miniaturization when synergistically integrating with microfluidics. However, implementation of LSPR biosensing for protein biomarker detection in complex clinical samples has still been prohibited primarily by a lack of balance between assay sensitivity and speed. Here, we have successfully overcome these challenges by synthesizing stripe-shaped assemblies of bioconjugated gold nanorod particles using microfluidic flow patterning, performing massively parallel on-chip binding assay with a biosensor-integrated optofluidic platform, and implementing high-throughput LSPR imaging for gold nanorod (AuNR) microarrays.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 1a shows our LSPR microarray biochip consisting of eight parallel microfluidic channels. These channels run orthogonal to six meandering stripes of antibody-functionalized AuNR ensembles with ten turns on a glass substrate. Specific antibodies were conjugated to the patterned AuNR microarrays using thiolated crosslinker and EDC/NHC chemistry. Each microfluidic channel can hold 250 nL in

Figure 1. a) Schematic of the LSPR microarray chip. b) Dark-field and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of AuNR biosensors fabricated and functionalized using a one-step microfluidic patterning technique assisted by electrostatic attractive interactions within microfluidic channels. c) The principle of the LSPR microarray imaging method.

volume and has inlet and outlet ports for reagent loading and washing. The chip design gives rise to an array of 480 stripe-shaped LSPR biosensing spots ($25 \text{ m} \times 200 \text{ m}$) on the entire chip. A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image in Fig. 1b validated that the LSPR sensing spots were coated with a disordered monolayer of AuNR particles at a surface number density of ~ 1 particles per $2.56 \mu\text{m}^2$, which corresponded to

an average particle-to-particle distance greater than 200 nm. The dispersed distribution of AuNRs effectively eliminates electromagnetic (EM) couplings between neighboring nanoparticles in the LSPR biosensing ensembles. As a result, the multi-arrayed LSPR sensor performance was solely determined by the superimposition of the optical characteristics of individual nanoparticles while uninfluenced

Figure 2. a) Calibration curves of TNF- α , IFN- γ , IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10 obtained from the LSPR microarray intensity mapping. The dashed lines represent the sigmoidal curves fitted to data points. b) Real-time AuNR microarray signals during multiplexed cytokine immunoassay, involving sample pre-loading, sample incubation, signal equilibration, and washing. c) Five-day cytokine concentration variations measured by the LSPR microarray assay for serum samples extracted from four post-cardiopulmonary cardiopulmonary bypass surgery pediatric patients.

by the disordered nanoparticle arrangement. It follows that the ensemble of $\sim 2,000$ plasmonically uncoupled AuNRs on each sensor spot could yield a scattering spectrum with a distinct resonance without particle-to-particle EM interferences, which led to the high sensitivity of our device. We employed dark-field imaging that scans the scattering light intensity across the LSPR biosensing spots for signal detection as illustrated in Fig. 1c. Analyte molecules were introduced to antibody-functionalized AuNR LSPR biosensors. Binding of the analyte molecules to the receptors induced a redshift and scattering intensity change for each AuNR biosensor. This intensity change across the ensemble of AuNR biosensors was collectively imaged via the characteristic optical band (grey area) using electron multiplying charge coupled device (EMCCD)-coupled dark-field microscopy. The detailed

fabrication method, principle and characterization of the LSPR microarray biosensor can be found in our previous study [7].

We further validate the developed microarray assay in a clinical relevant setting, where we successfully achieved multiplexed quantification of six cytokines (IL-2, IL-4, IL-6, IL-10, INF- α , and INF- γ) in human blood serum as shown in Fig. 2a with a limit of detection of ~ 10 pg/mL and a sample volume as small as $1 \mu\text{L}$ simultaneously using the 480 on-chip gold nanorod biosensing spots. Fig. 2b shows our label-free biosensor's ability to monitor analyte binding kinetics in real-time, which allows the total assay time to be shortened down to 15-30 min. Furthermore, our study validated our multiplex immunoassay by obtaining an excellent correlation with ELISA-based results.

Repair of congenital heart defects, the most common birth defect in the United States, necessitates open-heart

surgery using cardiopulmonary bypass (CPB) to supplant heart-lung function during surgery. Blood contact with the artificial surfaces of the CPB circuit is known to elicit a substantial inflammatory response in the immediate post-operative period that is normally restored to pre-operative levels within 48 hours after surgery. We collected serum samples prior to surgery (Pre) and on post-operative days one (D1), two (D2), three (D3), and four (D4) from two neonates undergoing congenital heart surgery with CPB and used our LSPR microarray immunoassay to quantify circulating serum cytokine levels in these samples as shown in Fig. 2c. We observed increased levels of both IL-6 and IL-10 on D1 following CPB in both patients although they were expressed at different levels. Post-operative heightening was also observed for IL-2, IL-4, TNF- α , and INF- γ in these patients on D1 or D2. The elevated cytokine expression was followed by a return to pre-operative levels of all the measured cytokines on D3 and D4. We also observed a very similar pattern to those previously reported where elevations in patient's serum cytokine levels most commonly return to pre-surgical levels within 48 hours of surgery. Such information has proven valuable since it is known that very high and/or prolonged expression of both pro-inflammatory (e.g. IL-6) and anti-inflammatory (e.g. IL-10) cytokines are associated with the acute immune dysfunction following cardiopulmonary bypass and can predict worse outcomes. This pattern of expression is thought to result from the host's misregulated compensatory effort to counter an initial pro-inflammatory response that occurs perioperatively as a result of cardiopulmonary bypass. Most importantly, the LSPR microarray assay has been shown to be able to detect variable degrees of responses in the four subjects after CPB.

III. CONCLUSION

The demonstrated label-free multiplexed immunoassay using our biosensing platform can serve as a powerful tool for

the detection of a wide spectrum of biomarkers relevant to human disease screening. The platform can also extend into the basic science arena providing small volume rapid detection of proteins from cell media or animal serum. The assay process is repeatable and easy to implement, which can readily be replicated by other research groups. To our best knowledge, this is the one of the very first studies to demonstrate practical implementation of LSPR-based nanobiosensing in a high throughput and multiplexed scheme for a clinically relevant setting. Enabled by such rapid cytokine-based immune status monitoring, we believe that our method will open the door for future personalized immunomodulatory therapy of systemic inflammatory diseases.

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